

Research Article

India, the US, and China as a Geopolitical Triangle

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Abstract: This article examines the complex interactions of the geopolitical triangle comprised of India, the United States, and China, investigating the multifaceted relationships and changing power dynamics among these significant global actors. Nowadays, interaction between these countries has become more and more crucial in influencing the geopolitical situation. This paper analyses the historical backdrop of their contacts, emphasizing the geopolitical, economic, and security aspects that shape their connections. Amidst changing global power dynamics, India emerges as a significant participant, maintaining a delicate equilibrium in its relationships with both the United States and China. The article examines India's strategic decision-making and diplomatic actions, considering its longstanding stance of non-alignment, economic ambitions, and worries regarding regional security. Simultaneously, the United States and China participate in an intricate interplay of collaboration and rivalry as their interests align and diverge across multiple domains. A fragile balance defines the geopolitical triangle, as each nation seeks its own national goals while managing the difficulties presented by regional and global intricacies. The article examines the influence of this triangular relationship on the stability of the area, economic collaborations, and security structures. Furthermore, it examines how new factors such as technology, trade, and climate change contribute to the formation of geopolitical dynamics among these nations.

Keywords: Geopolitics, US, India, China, Geopolitical landscape, Strategic Triangle

Introduction

The study of strategic triangles holds significant importance within the field of International Relations, although it has unfortunately received insufficient attention. During the historical period known as the Cold War, there was significant interest generated surrounding the evolving dynamics between the United States, the Soviet Union, and China, particularly within the context of their triangle connections (Gancheng, [2016](#)). The triads consisting of the United States, Pakistan, and India, China, Pakistan, and India, and the United States, Israel, and Arab states emerged as significant triangular connections within the regional context, impacting the stability of the bipolar power structure. Presently, it is imperative to direct increased academic focus toward the burgeoning and persistent trilateral alliances, namely the US–India–China, India–Japan–China, and China–Pakistan–India. A significant obstacle arises from the interconnection of certain triangular relationships, which may expand to include more states and hence transform into quadrilateral or bigger configurations involving several parties. The primary subject matter of this article pertains to the triangular connection between the United States, India, and China (Schmidt, [2014](#)). However, we also endeavour to examine the influence of other interconnected triangular dynamics on this relationship.

Strategic triangles are formed due to the interdependence that arises from the dynamics of conflict and cooperation among the three parties involved. Hence, it is imperative to examine them within the context of a comprehensive systemic analysis. From a systemic standpoint, alterations in one component of the triangle have an impact on the remaining components, with varying degrees of influence (Holmes et al., [2008](#)). Furthermore, according to Robert Jervis, the impacts of system effects might manifest in an indirect and delayed manner. The interactions among entities within a system are frequently not only influenced by two parties. The strategies used by states are contingent upon the strategies pursued by other actors. Additionally, the outcomes that arise may not necessarily align with the goals of the involved actors. The

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complexities of triangular systems can be particularly pronounced when many overlapping trilateral strategic interactions are present within a specific regional context.

Strategic triangles can be characterized as a close and interrelated association among three states, wherein their coexistence gives rise to a range of motivations and limitations for collaborative and confrontational actions among these states. In this context, each state perceives the other two as either being a source of security or a potential threat. Each of these governments is presumed to possess a significant degree of useable capability, often referred to as a strategic asset, particularly within the military domain. This capability is believed to have the potential to significantly influence the strategic trajectory of a given region. The inclusion of a second party in a trilateral scenario is predicated on the premise that the first state will enhance its own strength, influence, and bargaining capacity relative to the third state. A state may possess the ability to exercise an imbalanced degree of power and influence by virtue of its location in a pivotal geostrategic region, which grants it certain advantages over other actors within the strategic triangle.

Four strategic dimensions of trilateral relations are examined, with an emphasis on the India-US-China strategic triangle and its main manifestation, the balance of power. Understanding trilateral balancing in the modern world requires understanding hard, soft, and limited hard balancing (Malik, [2016](#)). Hard balancing involves formal alliances and military capabilities, while soft balancing uses international institutions, restricted agreements, and economic sanctions to constrain a threat or dominant entity. Limited hard balancing is a middle ground that relies on military strategic partnerships and asymmetrical weaponry growth. Academic practices require citations for content in Globalisation, and the near-unipolar security situation has changed great power and regional power balance methods. These considerations have created different state options and incentive systems, deviating from the typical balancing approach. The study will also discuss deterrence, weapons races, and status competition in a triangle of three states. This work analyses trilateral strategic interactions theoretically and empirically.

Research Objective

The research seeks to analyse the evolving geopolitical dynamics and strategic interactions among India, the United States, and China. More precisely, the analysis will centre on their economic, military, and diplomatic involvements and the possible consequences for the worldwide power equilibrium and regional stability.

Methodology

The research would be qualitative in nature. Secondary sources have been used to gather the information by studying research articles, books, newspapers, and other related materials.

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study lies in its capacity to offer valuable insights into the intricate dynamics of strategic interests, economic interdependencies, and diplomatic strategies among three major global powers. This analysis provides insight into the ways in which this three-way interaction affects the overall stability of global geopolitics, influences policies related to international trade and security, and forms the geopolitical dynamics of the current century. Comprehending these processes has significant importance for policymakers, scholars, and global leaders as they confront the complexities of a progressively multipolar global order.

Literature Review

Since the onset of the 21st century, concurrent with the recognition of the conclusion of the Cold War, there has been a notable movement in the global geopolitical and geo-economic focal point from the Atlantic Ocean to the presently designated Indo-Pacific Region. Subsequently, a significant portion of India's perspective has been primarily influenced by the framework of the India-China-US triangle, as well as the implications of the India-US alliance on New Delhi's interaction with an aggressive and formerly antagonistic neighbouring country, namely, China, and vice versa (Hornát, [2015](#)). The Chinese incursion in both Doklam (2017) and

Galwan (2020) has substantiated long-standing Indian fears (Khalid, 2020). The origins of the triangular discourse may be traced back to the Indo-US Civilian Nuclear Agreement of 2005, which led to the revision of existing worldwide legal standards on nuclear trade through a unique exception granted to India. This historical event marks the creation of the triangular discourse, although its roots can be found in earlier periods. Before things got better between New Delhi and Washington, the relationship between India and the US was not very polite and didn't involve anything important. A lot of people called it the "Nuclear Deal," but it was more than just a deal between India and the US to make it easy for them to work with other countries. India had not previously been included in this group prior to the agreement. Significant alterations occurred in the way the governments of both countries collaborated following this incident. Prior to 2005, India and the US had a predominantly South Asia-focused cooperation (Katti, 2007). Much of the discussion revolved around Washington's efforts to maintain a balanced and controlled relationship with both India and Pakistan. The United States also assumed the role of a self-proclaimed mediator in an effort to maintain tranquillity between the two nations.

The United States and India have entered into a significant agreement that officially alters their collaborative approach. The agreement also altered the manner in which the United States engages with South Asia. Prior to it, the United States had devised a strategy for addressing the South Asian region. It included managing its ties with both India and Pakistan and trying to keep things fair between the two countries at different times, as Washington saw fit. It was a big step forward for the US to try to keep its relationship with Pakistan separate from its relationship with India (Ghori, 2014). Things between China and India changed a lot, even though China said in public that it was worried and worked behind the scenes to help Pakistan become one of the few countries with nuclear weapons. At the start of the 21st century, New Delhi and Beijing made plans for how they would talk to each other (Yuan, 2011). This structure kept political differences at bay and pushed people to work together in many areas, especially when it came to trade and business. During this time, China's huge GDP growth and rise as a major economic power around the world made the country famous. Also, China was becoming more and more seen as a possible part of the new world order that formed after the Cold War. The US knew this, so in 2005, they suggested making a Group of Two (G-2) setup. This would be a casual way to get people to talk to and work with China. The main goal of G-2 was to work towards a non-Cold War between the two countries and get them to work together to solve problems in the world. A lot of people were interested in the G-2 at first, but it never really caught on and is now mostly forgotten. By the beginning of the 2010s, the United States "pivot" or "rebalancing" towards Asia had become an important part of its worldview (Hang, 2016). When the "Pivot to Asia" strategy was put into place, the US became more involved with a number of Asian countries. Australia, India, and Japan were the most obvious examples of this. Even though there were doubts at first, the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue, or Quad, tried to create an "Asian Arc of Democracy." Even though the Quad didn't say what it was for, it was seen as an anti-China conference that wanted to limit Beijing's power around the world.

The phrase "Indo-Pacific" inherently acknowledges China's involvement, considering its Asian roots, regional influence, and presence in the Pacific Ocean (Haruko, 2020#Haruko). A succession of subsequent developments has further strengthened the original doubts held by Beijing regarding the Quad. One prominent example of this phenomenon is the 'Malabar Naval Exercise' conducted in the Indian Ocean. Initially established as a bilateral exercise between India and the United States, it has since expanded to include all four members in the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad) (Smith, 2021). The linguistic convergence among the four states over their commitment to upholding a normative order based on established rules and the significance they attribute to maintaining freedom of navigation has not gone unnoticed, particularly in light of China's assertive and ambitious actions in the South China and East China seas. The initial concerns regarding China primarily stemmed from its emerging economic power and the implications it would have on the global stage. However, the geopolitical influence exerted by Beijing, supported by its robust economy, has become the main catalyst for the increasing anti-China sentiments observed in numerous international capitals, extending beyond those of the Quad. Prior to the official announcement of China's expansive global vision and the establishment of the 'Belt and Road Initiative' (BRI), the country had already established a significant international presence by investing in infrastructure projects

in developing nations, particularly in the Indo-Pacific Region, with a focus on port development (Yu, [2017](#)). Furthermore, the presence of the Chinese navy, particularly its submarines, in the remote regions of the Indian Ocean under the pretext of conducting anti-piracy operations, despite their inadequacy for such tasks, served to solidify concerns among various nations. These concerns encompassed the Quad nations, as well as countries in South and East Asia and Europe.

Nevertheless, the emergence of a power struggle in the Indian Ocean Region subsequently, coupled with the mere delineation of the Indo-Pacific Region, led to a shift in the global focal point away from the Atlantic. In this particular setting, the remaining three nations of the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue, under the leadership of the United States, acknowledged the potential role that India, as a resident middle power, can assume within the area. The significance of India lies in its geopolitical and military role as a counterbalance to China, as well as its status as a viable investment option. Additionally, India possesses intrinsic characteristics that might potentially propel it to become a major contributor to the global economy, similar to China's previous trajectory. India's misgivings towards China, coupled with unresolved bilateral conflicts and potential foreign investment opportunities, as well as the imperative to protect its strategic sphere of influence from Chinese expansion, have contributed to the consideration of both concepts.

The Indo-Pacific region and the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue (Quad) present an appealing proposition (Panda, [2020](#)). The presence of shared interests and concerns, along with the assumption of a restricted capacity for East Asian nations to influence the developing Asian security framework, led to the identification of India, China, and the United States as the primary actors creating the region's security architecture. The process of removing hyphens from the Trilateral Quagmire. In recent decades, New Delhi has effectively disassociated India from Pakistan, thereby altering the worldwide picture of the country. There has been notable progress in garnering acceptance of the new construct within the Islamic world, particularly in influencing powerful nations such as Saudi Arabia to distance themselves from Pakistan in recent months. Nevertheless, India's association with China, the US, or any other nation is likely to pose a challenge. India's foreign policy dynamics have developed based on the principles of sovereign independence in decision-making and strategic autonomy in military affairs. The underlying motivation for the concept of 'strategic autonomy' extends beyond India's imagined notion of sovereignty. India's pursuit of an autonomous foreign policy has been further strengthened in the post-Independence era.

The Indian establishment has adhered to the notion of an "independent foreign policy" since its founding. This course of action presents India with the option to engage in bilateral relations with several nations, free from the constraints imposed by third-party meddling. India places a significant emphasis on the distinctiveness of its bilateral relationships with other nations worldwide and endeavours to uphold the exceptional connection that accompanies them. India's commitment to the Non-Aligned Movement in the past and its reluctance to disengage from it presently can be attributed to this precise rationale. When considering the relationship between China, the United States, and India, it is evident that New Delhi possesses both areas of disagreement and shared interests with both Beijing and Washington (Madan, [2017](#)). The development of India's bilateral relations with both nations has occurred apart from one another. However, there is a widely held opinion that India should avoid being manipulated as a strategic tool by other powers, such as the United States, and should also strive to prevent being a casualty of such geopolitical manoeuvring. Hence, it is imperative to critically examine India's involvement with China and the United States, focusing on bilateral relations rather than a hyphenated trilateral equation and doing so promptly.

Historical Context

The historical backdrop of the geopolitical triangle encompassing India, the United States, and China is a complex account influenced by changes in geopolitical power, ideological reorientations, and regional dynamics. The Cold War era signalled the beginning phases of this triadic interaction. India, under the leadership of Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru, used a policy called "non-alignment" to stay separate from the ideological fights going on between the US and the USSR (Rauch, [2008](#)). The United States made a strong alliance with Pakistan during this time, which caused relations between India and the United States to change. China used to be connected to the Soviet Union. When the Soviet Union and China broke up, China's global

direction changed drastically. The border disagreement between China and India in 1962 made things more complicated in the area. In the years after the end of the Cold War, India liberalised its economy, which made it change its foreign policy. The US tried to improve ties with India because it understood its strategic importance and economic potential. China's economic changes made it famous around the world and changed the political situation at the same time. India and the U.S. have become closer in the 21st century because they both care about economic growth and democracy (Comeau, [2003](#)). But they also said they were worried about China's aggressive actions in the Indo-Pacific region. In this already difficult geopolitical triangle, there are also ongoing disagreements in the region, such as the one between India and Pakistan, and tensions along the border between India and China. These disagreements show how their past acts still affect how they interact with each other now.

India, the US, and China all played a big role in the big changes in geopolitics that happened after the Cold War. When India opened up its economy in the early 1990s, it opened up new ways to interact with the rest of the world (Cohen, [1991](#)). This led the country to actively seek out a wider range of relationships. In its foreign policy after the Cold War, the US recognised how important it was to build ties with countries whose economies were growing, like India. There was agreement on this fact because of shared goals in fighting terrorism, trade, and a commitment to democratic values. On the other hand, China's quick rise to become the world's largest economy and its confident participation in international issues began to change the way the triangle worked. The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and China's growing power in the South China Sea have changed the way power is distributed in the area and around the world in big ways. As worries about things like human rights, trade deficits, and intellectual property rights became more important in the triangle relationship, tensions and strategic competition grew. It's helpful to know about the history of the interactions between the three states in order to fully grasp how complicated their relationship is now. This background information helps us understand the economic, military, and diplomatic sides of this geopolitical triangle. The past is still having an effect on how these interactions change, and this will decide how the geopolitical environment looks in the years to come. In the background of these historical events, the geopolitical triangle, which is made up of India, the US, and China, is very complicated because of the way regional dynamics and battles affect each other. The enduring India-Pakistan war has not only moulded India's regional security worries but has also impacted its strategic alliances. The United States, which has been a significant ally of Pakistan throughout history, has endeavoured to maintain a delicate equilibrium in its relationships with both neighbouring countries in South Asia, so adding to the complexities of regional geopolitics (Tanzeem, [2016](#)). The ongoing border conflicts between India and China, including the current tensions in the Himalayan region, emphasise the enduring difficulties and possible areas of conflict inside the triangular area. Simultaneously, the United States has been more engaged and formed security alliances in the Indo-Pacific region due to its strategic concerns in the South China Sea. This aligns with India's objective of promoting a free and unrestricted Indo-Pacific. The alignment of interests has strengthened the strategic alliance between India and the United States, adding a maritime aspect to the geopolitical triangle.

The future direction of the geopolitical triangle is unknown, with various conceivable scenarios. The economic interconnectedness among the three nations, namely within the framework of global supply chains, has the potential to promote collaboration. However, there are problems arising from strategic competition, notably in the realm of technology. The changing dynamics will not only impact the regional distribution of power but also have extensive consequences for global governance, trade, and security. Given the ongoing influence of previous events on current geopolitics, it is crucial to have a detailed comprehension of the historical background in order to comprehend the complex network of relationships within the India-U.S.-China geopolitical triangle.

Current Geopolitical Landscape

The geopolitical dynamics among India, the United States, and China create a multifaceted and ever-changing triangle relationship that has significant ramifications for global politics, economy, and security. India, being a prominent actor in South Asia, has experienced substantial economic expansion and diplomatic sway. The country's foreign policy demonstrates a nuanced equilibrium, aiming to establish strategic alliances with

both the United States and China. The bilateral ties between India and the United States have significantly deepened in recent years, propelled by a common commitment to democratic principles and mutual strategic objectives, particularly in the Indo-Pacific area. India concurrently maintains commercial relations with China, highlighting collaboration while occasionally experiencing problems, particularly in relation to territorial conflicts (Konwer, [2011](#)). The United States, a dominant force on the global stage, exerts significant influence in defining the geopolitical dynamics of the triangle. The US has made dealing with the problems caused by China's rise a top priority. As part of its plan, it has strengthened partnerships and alliances across the Indo-Pacific area, with India playing a key role. In their partnership, the US and China depend on each other economically and compete with each other in geopolitics. Concerns about human rights, trade disagreements, and competition in technology all play a part in the complex and far-reaching global dynamics.

On the other hand, China has quickly grown into a major economic and military power, which is a threat to the US's long-held position as the world's most powerful country (Art, [2010](#)). The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) shows that China wants to increase its power around the world through building projects. China is involved in both working together and competing with other countries in the global triangle. India and the U.S. work together on the economy even though their borders sometimes clash. On the other hand, the U.S. and China have a complicated relationship that includes trade talks, competition in technology, and political conflict, especially in the Indo-Pacific region. India, the United States, and China are all parts of this geopolitical triangle. How they connect with each other has big and far-reaching effects. The unstable balance of power affects the stability of the area and the world. It is affected by military posturing, economic interests, and new technologies. The geopolitical situation changes as countries deal with each other, which affects events around the world in the 21st century. The relationships in this global triangle are complicated because they involve both cooperation and competition. This makes it important to study the situation carefully and plan ahead strategically.

The economic parts of the geopolitical triangle are especially interesting. India wants to use its strong economy to improve its place in the world, which has many different types of industries and is growing quickly. The country trades and invests with both the US and China, hoping to get the most out of its economic partnerships (Fordham et al., [2011](#)). Meanwhile, the United States and China, as the two largest economies in the world, participate in an intricate choreography of economic interdependence and rivalry. Trade tensions, technology disputes, and worries regarding intellectual property rights influence the complex economic connection between the two countries. These factors have significant effects on global markets and industries. Within the domain of technology, the triangle dynamics are vividly evident. The United States and China are engaged in a technical competition that encompasses various domains, including 5G, artificial intelligence, and cyber capabilities. India, acknowledging the significance of technological progress, aims to establish partnerships with other countries while exercising caution to safeguard its own interests. The tech competition holds significant consequences for worldwide innovation, cyber security, and the advancement of developing technologies that will influence the future. Security considerations further complicate the geopolitical triangle. India, located in a region characterised by historical animosities and ongoing hostilities, carefully manages a precarious equilibrium to safeguard its security and territorial sovereignty. The United States, observing China's wary military expansion, is actively pursuing strategic alliances to counteract its impact (Xinbo, [2000](#)). China is actively pursuing its objectives in the South China Sea and other areas by undergoing a process of military modernization, which further complicates the security situation.

Security Dynamics

The security dynamics within the geopolitical triangle, including India, the United States, and China, are complex and diverse, influenced by historical animosities, regional disputes, and the pursuit of strategic objectives. India, located in an intricate region with long-standing enemies, places great importance on security as a fundamental aspect of its foreign policy. The nation confronts enduring obstacles, such as territorial conflicts with China, specifically along the Himalayan frontier. India's military modernization efforts and strategic cooperation, particularly with the U.S., are motivated by territorial concerns and the aim to

offset China's dominance in the region. The United States, being a dominant global power, has a crucial influence on the security dynamics within the triangle. The United States is worried about China's increasing military presence and aggressive behaviour in the Indo-Pacific region (Mastro, [2020](#)). As a result, the U.S. is actively pursuing strategic alliances and partnerships to guarantee stability in the area. The security alliance between the United States and India has experienced substantial enhancement, driven by mutual concerns in combating terrorism, safeguarding maritime security, and upholding the international order based on established laws. The Quadrilateral Security Dialogue, which includes the United States, India, Japan, and Australia, serves as a prime example of endeavours to bolster security collaboration and discourage possible threats presented by China.

China, despite emphasising a non-aggressive ascent, has undertaken military modernization efforts, enhancing its naval capacities and making territorial assertions in the South China Sea. These acts exacerbate regional anxiety and prompt neighbouring countries, such as India, to enhance their security measures. The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) of China has significant strategic ramifications, as there are concerns regarding the use of debt-trap diplomacy and the possibility of critical infrastructure projects being militarized. The interplay of these variables, together with sporadic border conflicts, contributes to the complex security dynamics inside the geopolitical triangle. The interrelated nature of security threats extends beyond conventional military considerations. Cybersecurity and technology improvements have a substantial impact. The United States and China are currently involved in a competitive race to develop advanced technology, which has significant consequences for both countries' national security and their positions as world leaders in technology. India, recognising the significance of cybersecurity, aims to address these difficulties while leveraging technology progress for its own progress. The security dynamics within the geopolitical triangle, including India, the U.S., and China, are influenced by historical backdrop, territorial disputes, and the pursuit of strategic objectives. As these countries strive to maintain a delicate equilibrium between collaboration and rivalry, the changing security situation has significant consequences for both regional stability and the wider global framework. The interaction between military displays, alliances, and technical progress is the key factor in shaping the security dynamics inside this crucial geopolitical triangle.

Economic Interdependency

The economic interconnectedness between India, the United States, and China is a crucial and intricate component of the geopolitical triangle, which has a significant impact on global commerce, investment patterns, and economic stability. India, with its burgeoning and heterogeneous economy, actively participates in economic collaborations with both the United States and China. India and the U.S. have developed a strong economic relationship in recent years, with a focus on industries such as information technology, pharmaceuticals, and energy. The U.S. is an important trading partner for India. China has emerged as a significant participant in India's economic domain, establishing trade and investment links despite intermittent conflicts, particularly along the border.

The economic relationship between the United States and China is a highly significant determinant of the global economy (Jiang et al., [2019](#)). Being the two largest economies in the world, they have a strong mutual dependence. The United States is a significant purchaser of Chinese products, whereas China possesses a considerable amount of debt from the United States. Nevertheless, this economic interdependence persists alongside strategic conflict. Global markets and industries are affected by tensions arising from trade disputes, intellectual property concerns, and technical rivalry. The economic interdependence between the United States and China significantly influences the overall economic dynamics inside the geopolitical triangle. The economic dynamics inside this triangle transcend beyond two-way partnerships to embrace wider regional and global aspects. India, the United States, and China are all participants with vested interests in multiple international organisations and forums, where matters pertaining to economic policy, trade agreements, and development projects are deliberated upon. As nations prioritise their economic interests, the choices made in international forums have far-reaching effects on the geopolitical environment, shaping diplomatic ties and geopolitical alliances. Technological interdependence plays a crucial role in the economic dynamics within the triangle. The United States and China are involved

in a technical rivalry that encompasses various domains like 5G, artificial intelligence, and semiconductor fabrication. India acknowledges the significance of technical progress for its economic growth and strategically engages in partnerships and collaborations with other countries. It prudently handles the potential advantages and disadvantages that come with technological dependency. The intricate economic interconnectedness among the three geopolitical entities forms a fragile equilibrium characterised by a blend of collaboration and rivalry. Economic interdependencies foster stability and prosperity, whereas geopolitical conflicts can result in disruptions and uncertainties. The interaction of economic interests determines the tactics and policies of each nation, impacting not just their internal economies but also the wider global economic system. The economic interconnectedness between India, the U.S., and China is a crucial issue that demands cautious navigation and strategic vision, given the evolving geopolitical situation.

Future Scenario

To analyze the future scenarios involving India, the United States, and China as a geopolitical triangle, we need to examine the possible developments in politics, economics, technology, and security. A conceivable possibility is a heightened strategic convergence between India and the United States, as they both aim to counteract China's escalating influence. This alignment may encompass enhanced security cooperation, economic alliances, and synchronised endeavours to sustain a globally recognized system based on established principles and regulations. This situation might potentially result in the strengthening of the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue and an increase in diplomatic interactions between Washington and New Delhi. Alternatively, a contrasting future scenario could entail a more intricate equilibrium where India upholds a certain level of strategic independence, interacting with both the U.S. and China according to specific interests. India may exploit its position to derive economic advantages from both great nations, hence sustaining economic interdependence. India would need to demonstrate skilled diplomacy in order to effectively manage the intricate dynamics of the rivalry between the United States and China, all while protecting its own national interests.

Another probable future entails a re-evaluation of connections characterized by swift changes in geopolitical dynamics. Changes in leadership, unexpected global events, or movements in public opinion could modify any of the three nations' geopolitical calculations. An instance in which India adopts a more proactive stance in regional matters, assuming a position of leadership in South Asia, has the potential to fundamentally alter the dynamics of the triangle. This could include a re-evaluation of alliances and partnerships, perhaps resulting in a restructuring of power distribution in the Indo-Pacific region. Economic scenarios are equally crucial. Should the United States and China successfully mitigate their trade tensions and reach a consensus on global economic governance, a potentially more stable economic climate may ensue. On the other hand, if commercial disagreements get more intense, it could result in a division of global supply chains. This would not only affect the economic interdependence inside the triangle but also have a widespread influence on the global economy. Technological situations have the potential to either diverge or converge. In a potential scenario of heightened technical rivalry, the world may witness a divided global technology terrain characterized by separate domains of dominance spearheaded by the United States and China. Conversely, cooperative endeavours in domains such as climate change, space exploration, or global health could facilitate technological collaboration, resulting in mutual progress that surpasses geopolitical conflicts. Security situations are essential factors to take into account. The potential escalation of regional tensions, particularly between India and China, may have significant implications for the geopolitical terrain (Markey, [2021](#)). Alternatively, a collective endeavour to resolve conflicts and implement measures to develop trust could cultivate a more secure environment, enabling a heightened emphasis on common issues such as terrorism, cyber threats, and pandemics.

The future prospects of India, the U.S., and China as a geopolitical triangle are fundamentally unclear, influenced by a multitude of circumstances. Future developments will be influenced by the decisions and behaviours of these countries, the worldwide geopolitical situation, and their capacity to handle intricate circumstances. The geopolitical triangle will remain a fundamental aspect of international relations, and its

potential outcomes will have significant consequences for global stability, economic well-being, and the structure of the international system in the future.

Conclusion

Exploring political, economic, technological, and security scenarios for India, the US, and China as a geopolitical triangle is necessary. India and the US may strengthen their strategic alliance to counterbalance China's rise. This alignment could encompass deeper security, economic, and rules-based international order cooperation. Washington and New Delhi may strengthen the Quadrilateral Security Dialogue and boost diplomatic relations. Alternatively, India might maintain strategic autonomy and engage with the U.S. and China based on its interests. India may use its position to profit from both great nations in economic interdependence. India would need skilful diplomacy to handle the U.S.-China rivalry while protecting its interests. Recalibrating ties when geopolitical forces change swiftly is another possibility. Any of the three nations' geopolitical calculus could change due to leadership, global events, or public opinion. India's leadership in South Asia could change the triangle's dynamics. This may require reassessing alliances and partnerships and redistributing Indo-Pacific power. Economic possibilities matter, too. A more stable economy might result if the U.S. and China can reduce trade hostilities and agree on global economic governance. A strengthening of commercial disagreements could bifurcate global supply networks, affecting the triangle's economic interdependence and the world economy. Technological scenarios may diverge or converge. As technical competition grows, the U.S. and China may lead separate technological domains. Climate change, space exploration, and global health collaborations could lead to technological cooperation and geopolitical progress.

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